

APPLICATION OF MOBILE GAMES IN THE PREPARATION PROCESS YOUNG FOOTBALL PLAYERS

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Annotation: The article is devoted to the study of the effectiveness of the use of outdoor games in the educational and training process of young football players at the stage of initial training of the third year of study. The structure and content of the training sessions for football players involved in groups of initial training are considered. The main means of developing the physical, technical and tactical preparedness of football players at this stage of training are given. The use of specialized outdoor games and relay races as priority training means is substantiated.

Key words: sports training of football players at the initial stage, the main means of developing the physical, technical and tactical readiness of football players, specialized outdoor games and relay races in the training process of football players.

Introduction. At the stage of initial training of football players, the versatile orientation of the training process is effective. The priority areas in training are the development of physical qualities, the acquisition of technology and initial tactics of actions [1, 2, 3]. At this time, the training of 7-10-year-old football players is carried out mainly with the help of exercises available for children of this age. You should not conduct a large number of exercises, do not require them to be performed at the maximum pace, master more than 2-3 techniques in one session, conduct two-sided games on fields of standard sizes in generally accepted compositions. Excessive use of highly specialized tools and methods often hinders the growth of mastery at subsequent stages [4, 5, 6].

At this stage, at the training sessions for the physical training of young football players, along with the development of general physical qualities, special ones are improved, and the use of specialized outdoor games and relay races in the training process has a positive effect, since they increase the density of classes and significantly increase the load [6, 7, 8]. At this time, young football players are introduced to the basic technical techniques that allow them to successfully conduct elementary game activities. For the formation and development of game thinking, it is necessary to use a wide range of means, including outdoor games, aimed at developing the speed of a complex reaction, orientation, and the ability to interact with partners [11, 12, 14].

It should be noted that when determining training facilities at the stage of initial training, special attention should be paid to the careful selection of games and relay races for football players and thinking through their content. They must be interesting, different in complexity and accessible, have a competitive nature and correspond to the direction of the game of football. There are imitative outdoor games, that is, with imitative actions; outdoor games with dashes, overcoming obstacles, with a ball, sticks and other objects; outdoor games with resistance and orientation by auditory and visual signals. The choice of this or that game is determined by the specific tasks and conditions of the training session [9, 10, 13]. Next, we present the main means of general and special physical, technical and tactical training used in the educational and training process of the football players who took part in the pedagogical study. When choosing means, we were guided by the recommendations presented in the exemplary program of sports training for football players for children's and youth sports schools, specialized children's and youth schools of the Olympic reserve [15].

The main means of developing the general physical fitness of football players at the initial stage of training.

1. Combat exercises: the main stance, standing in a column and line, one at a time independently and at the signal of the teacher for a while. Opening in column and line, on the spot and in motion Turns on the spot. Exercises for the formation of posture, the prevention of flat feet. General developmental exercises with an object (ball, rope, gymnastic stick) and without an object.
2. Varieties of walking (on toes, heels, internal, external arch of the foot, rolls from heel to toe, jumps, in a semi-squat, squat, with wide steps, lunges left and right, with body turns left and right).
3. Running in various directions, smooth, with a change in step width, speed, side steps, backwards, mincing, with a stop at the teacher's signal, with the teacher's task, with an object in hand.
4. Jumping on two and one leg in place, moving forward, in length, from a height of 20 cm, 30 cm. Jumping onto a gymnastic mat no more than 30-40 cm high.
5. Acrobatic and gymnastic exercises: tucking, tucked rolls, lying on the stomach and from an emphasis while kneeling, standing on toes, on one leg on the floor and on the gymnastic bench, walking on the gymnastic bench, stepping over balls, turning 90 degrees , walking on the rail of a gymnastic bench, steps with jumps, side steps, a side gallop step, combinations and complexes of general developmental exercises of varying coordination complexity.
6. Sports games according to simplified rules - mini-football [4].

The main means of developing the special physical fitness of football players at the initial stage of training.

1. Development of flexibility - general developmental exercises with a wide range of motion. Exercises with the help of a partner (passive bends, abductions of legs, arms to the limit, half-twine, twine), exercises with a gymnastic stick or a rope folded in four: tilts, turns of the torso with various positions of objects (up, down, behind the head, behind the back); stepping and jumping, twists and circles. Exercises on the gymnastic wall, gymnastic bench.

2. Development of speed qualities - repeated running over a distance of 10-15 m, from the start and immediately with a maximum speed of 10 to 30 m. Running down an inclined plane.
3. Development of coordination abilities - multidirectional movements of arms and legs, somersaults forward, to the sides from a place. Blade stand. Balance exercises. Juggling with two or three tennis balls with hands, juggling with the right and left legs (middle, inner and outer parts of the lift, thigh). Throwing balls at a stationary target, throwing after somersaults, rolls.
4. Development of strength abilities - exercises with overcoming one's own weight, pulling up from the hang, push-ups, squats on one and two legs. Rope climbing, stairs. Rope pulling. Medicine ball exercises.
5. Development of endurance - uniform and variable run for 500 m, dosed run over rough terrain. Skiing up and down. Swimming [17, 18].

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The main means of developing the technical readiness of football players at the initial stage of training.

1. Throwing the ball with your hands at a distance and into a corridor 2 m wide, hitting the ball (stationary, moving) with your right, left foot. Shots on goal. Movements: normal, side steps, dribbling the ball with the foot, stopping the ball only with the right or only the left foot, deceptive movements, tackling the ball, hitting the ball with the head. Playing football according to simplified rules, outdoor

games in the form of relay races using elements and techniques of ball possession.

Mobile games with football elements.

2. Technique of movement. Running: normal, backwards, cross and side steps, in a straight line and arcs, with a change in direction and speed. Jumps: up, up forward, up back, up left, up right, push with two legs from a place, push with one and two legs from a running start. For goalkeepers - jumping to the side with a roll fall. Turns: stepping, jumping, on the supporting leg, to the sides and back, in place and in motion. Stops while running lunge and jump.

3. Kicking the ball. Strikes with the inside of the foot, the inside and middle of the instep, on a stationary ball and rolling (towards, away from the player, to the right or left). Hitting a bouncing and flying ball with the inside of the foot and the middle part of the instep. Striking with the outside of the instep. Making shots after stopping, jerking, dribbling, faking, sending the ball down and over, for a short and medium distance. Hits for accuracy: at a specific target on the field, at the goal, at the feet of a partner, at the move of a moving partner.

4. Stopping the ball. Stopping with the sole and the inside of the foot of a rolling and falling ball - in place, in motion forward and backward. Stopping the ball flying towards the inside of the foot, thigh, chest. A stop with a transfer to the sides, preparing the ball for subsequent actions and covering it with the body from the opponent.

5. Dribbling. Leading the inside and outside of the lift. Driving with the right, left foot and alternately, in a straight line and in a circle, with a change in direction of movement, between racks and moving partners, with a change in speed, with accelerations and jerks, without losing control of the ball.

6. Deceptive movements (feints). "Leaving" with a lunge (when attacking the enemy from the front, the ability to show the movement of the body in one direction and leave with the ball in the other). "Stopping" the ball (after slowing down and a false

attempt to stop the ball with the foot, making a jerk with the ball). “Kick” on the ball (imitation of kicking the ball and leaving it away from the opponent).

Conclusions. So, the importance of outdoor games in the sports training of young football players is difficult to overestimate. In essence, we are talking about using the most effective game method for a given age. By its very nature, the game unobtrusively encourages its participants to use their knowledge, skills and abilities more deeply and more fully in coordinated actions with teammates, develops attention, operational thinking, a sense of collectivism, responsibility, mutual assistance and many other socially important and useful qualities. In this regard, outdoor games selected for training should help to master or consolidate the necessary knowledge, skills and abilities of football.

Regularly playing special outdoor games methodically correctly selected by the coach, young football players master technical skills faster and more efficiently, learn to analyze the current situation, and develop physical abilities. To increase the effectiveness of the training process, it is necessary to select such games in which all the players take part at the same time and the content of the game can be easily and quickly varied - complicated or simplified at the discretion of the coach, based on the specific sports situation. Thus, outdoor games occupy a special place in the process of sports training of young football players at the stage of initial training, developing in a complex physical and technical qualities necessary for future athletes.

References:

1. Kurbanmuratovich, U. M. (2022). The efficiency of the experimental methods of improving complex technical and tactical actions of boxers. *ASEAN Journal of Physical Education and Sport Science*, 1(1), 17-24.
2. Usmonov, M. (2019). Role and place of individual lessons in the general boxing training system. *International journal of advanced research*, 7(12), 955-958.

3. Mansur, U. (2019). role and place of individual lessons in the general boxing training system *Int. J. of Adv. Res*, 7, 955-958.
4. Mansur, U. (2022). Determination of the ability of boxers to work through pulse oximeter and chronometry during boxing. *Modern Journal of Social Sciences and Humanities*, 4, 230-232.
5. Mansur, U. (2023). Analysis of Boxers' Pulse Oximeter and Chronometry Ability to Perform During Boxing. *ASEAN Journal of Physical Education and Sport Science*, 2(1), 69-74.
6. Mansur, U. (2022). Distribution of Training Loads in The Annual Cycle of Training of Highly Qualified Boxers. *ASEAN Journal of Physical Education and Sport Science*, 1(1), 43-50.
7. Xalmuxamedov, R. D., Maxmudova, M. M., & Usmonov, M. Q. (2021). Specific features of the use of uzbek marty art methods and methods in physical education classes of higher educational institutions *int. j. of adv. res.* 9 (jan). 1166-1170](issn 2320-5407).
8. Halmukhamedov, R. D. (2022). Training loads of boxers in individual lessons on "paws" and their evaluation. *Texas Journal of Medical Science*, 15, 27-34.
9. Turdimurodov, D. Y. (2023, April). Development of volitional qualities of personality in children of junior school age through sports. In *International scientific conference "Scientific advances and innovative approaches"* (Vol. 1, No. 1, pp. 104-110).
10. Turdimurodov, D. Y. (2023). The role of the learning and game environment in the formation of volitional qualities in physical education lessons. *Modern Scientific Research International Scientific Journal*, 1(4), 38-45.
11. Yuldashevich, T. D. Formation of Volitional Qualities of Preschool Children in the Process of Physical Education. *nature*, 1, 2.
12. Yuldashevich, T. D. Volitional Qualities as a Means of Physical Education of a Personality.

13. Yuldashevich, T. D. (2023). Development of Volitional Qualities of Students of Pedagogical University by Means of Physical Education. *American journal of science and learning for development*, 2(6), 62-65.
14. Абдуллаев, Я. М., & Турдимуродов, Д. Й. (2020). Ўсмир ёшдаги ўқувчиларда продавий сифатларни жисмоний тарбия воситалари орқали ривожлантириш. *Современное образование (Узбекистан)*, (9 (94)), 56-62.
15. Абдуллаев, Я. М., & Юлдашевич, Т. Д. (2020). Создание педагогических условий в формировании волевых качеств у учеников начальных классов. In *Colloquium-journal* (No. 24 (76), pp. 36-38). Голопристанський міськрайонний центр зайнятості.
16. Усмонов, М. (2022). Типовые методы дозирования нагрузок и отдыха в работе боксёров на «лапах». *Архив научных исследований*, 5(5).
17. Усмонов, М. К. (2021). Роль индивидуальных занятий на " лапах " в общей системе подготовки боксёров. *Fan-Sportga*, (5), 18-21.
18. Усмонов, М. К., & Турдиев, А. Г. (2018). Боксчининг рухий жараёнининг ривожланишини хусусиятлари. In *Молодой исследователь: вызовы и перспективы* (pp. 353-357).